

A convenient and expeditious synthesis of annulated *N*, *S*-heterocycles[†]

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A convenient synthesis of thieno[2,3-*b*]pyridines (3), thieno[3,2-*c*]pyridines (4), pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines (6), thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (9), pyrido[1,2-*a*]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (11), pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (12), pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidines (13) and pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimido[1,2-*a*]pyrimidines (14) has been described starting from the reaction of suitably functionalized pyridines (1, 2), pyrimidines (7), and pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimidines (10) with different nucleophiles in sequence of reactions.

Pyrimidines and purines being an integral part of DNA and RNA occupy significant place in medicinal and pharmaceutical chemistry due to their diverse pharmacological properties. The therapeutic importance of pyrimidines and annulated pyrimidine derivatives as antibacterial¹, antitumor², antiinflammatory³, antifungal⁴, and cardiovascular⁵ agents aroused considerable interest to synthesize thienopyridines, thienopyrimidines, pyrazolopyridines, pyrazolopyrimidines and pyrimidopyrimidines as isosteres of purine and pteridines.

2(1*H*)-Pyridone, being basic structural unit of various pharmacologically active compounds^{6,7}, has drawn great deal of attention to the synthesis of a variety of annulated heterocycles^{8,9} of therapeutic importance. The presence of alkylthio and nitrile functionalities in the molecular make-up of 2(1*H*)-pyridone, made it susceptible to nucleophile for various transformations to condensed heterocycles. Earlier, 2(1*H*)-pyridones have been prepared from the reaction of α -oxoketene dithioacetals with ethyl cyanoacetate¹⁰⁻¹³. However, this method has limitation of obtaining inaccessible α -oxoketene dithioacetals and its high reactivity towards nucleophiles. Later on, 2(1*H*)-pyridones have been synthesized¹⁴ through replacement of acidic proton from active methyl or methylene compounds by 2-cyano-3,3-dimethylthioacrylamide or 2-cyano-3,3'-dimethylthioacrylonitrile, followed by ring closer to yield 6-aryl-4-methylsulfanyl-2(1*H*)-pyridones (1) which on halogenation with POCl₃ yield 6-aryl-2-chloro-3-cyano-4-methyl-sulfanylpyridines (2). The chloropyridine being very reactive, smoothly reacts to form substitution products with ethyl mercaptoacetate and hydrazine hydrate, followed by cyclization.

Ethyl mercaptoacetate as a reagent for the synthesis of annulated thienopyridines and thienopyrimidines has not been extensively studied. Here, we report the versatility of the reagent for the construction of condensed sulfur heterocycles (3, 4, 9, 11, 12) (Schemes 1-3). Thus, 6-aryl-3-cyano-4-methylsulfanyl-1*H*-pyridin-2-ones (1) on reaction with ethyl mercaptoacetate underwent base-catalyzed condensation-cyclization reaction to yield ethyl 3-amino-6-aryl-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[3,2-*c*]pyridine-2-carboxylates (4) which on alkylation with methyl iodide led to yield ethyl 3-amino-6-[4-bromophenyl]-7-cyano-5-methyl-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[3,4-*c*]pyridine-2-carboxylate (5). Similarly, 6-aryl-2-chloro-3-cyano-4-methylsulfanylpyridines (2) on reaction with ethyl mercaptoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide at reflux temperature yielded regioselectively ethyl 3-amino-6-aryl-4-ethoxycarbonylmethylsulfanylthieno[2,3-*b*]pyrimidine-2-carboxylates (3). There are two possible modes of cyclization of ethoxycarbonylmethylsulfanyl substituents present at positions 2 and 4 with cyano group. According to the first option, cyclization involves the attack of carbanion generated from ethoxycarbonylmethylsulfanyl substituents at position 2 on cyano group to form 3, while under the second option, cyclization may take place involving ethoxycarbonylmethylsulfanyl substituents at position 4 with cyano functionality to yield ethyl 3-amino-6-aryl-4-ethoxycarbonylmethylsulfanylthieno[3,2-*c*]pyridine-2-carboxylates (3'). The stepwise synthesis ascertained the structure of isolated compound as 3. The ¹H NMR of one of the synthesized compounds 3a showed two triplets at δ 1.23 and 1.39 which were assigned for protons of two methyl groups of ethoxycarbonyl and ethoxycarbonylmethylsulfanyl groups. Two quartets at δ 4.17 and 4.36 were ascertained

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Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions : (i) POCl₃/120°, (ii) HSCH₂COOC₂H₅/NaOC₂H₅/100°, (iii) CH₃I/K₂CO₃/DMF, (iv) N₂H₄·H₂O/C₂H₅OH/100°.

Scheme 2

for two methylene groups. A sharp singlet at δ 4.2 and a broad singlet at δ 6.70 were assigned for a methylene and amino groups. Two doublets at δ 7.44 and 7.98 were ascertained for two aromatic protons each, while singlet at δ 7.70 was assigned for one pyridine ring proton. Reaction of chloropyridines (2) with ambiphilic nucleophile, hydrazine hydrate yielded 3-amino-6-aryl-methylsulfanyl-1*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines (6). In this reaction methylsulfanyl substituent at position 4 did not participate in nucleophilic

substitution reaction.

The use of ethyl mercaptoacetate as a reagent was further explored for the preparation of thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (9) from the reaction with 5-cyano-6-methylsulfanylpuridines (7). Similarly, 2-methylsulfanyl-4-oxo-4*H*-pyrimido[1,2-*a*]pyrimidine-3-carbonitriles (10) on base-catalyzed condensation-cyclization reaction with ethyl mercaptoacetate at reflux temperature provided pyrido[1,2-*a*]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (11) which was further cyclized

Scheme 3. Reagents and conditions : (i) NaOC₂H₅/C₂H₅OH/100°, (ii) HCONH₂/180° (iii) NH₂C(=NH)NHCN/100°, (iv) N₂H₄·H₂O/C₂H₅OH.

to a tetracyclic heterocycle, 9-methyl-12*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine-4,12(3*H*)-dione by refluxing in formamide.

The reaction of **10** with dicyandiamide, a 1,3-ambiphilic nucleophile under basic condition yielded 4-amino-5-oxo-5*H*-pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidin-2-ylcyanamides (**13**) while reaction with hydrazine hydrate provided 3-amino-7-methylpyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimido[1,2-*a*]pyrimidin-4(1*H*)-ones (**14**).

Experimental

M.p.s were determined on a Büchi-530 instrument in open capillary and are uncorrected. The reagent grade reaction solvent DMF was further purified and dried following literature procedures. Cyanamide was purchased from Aldrich. TLC was performed on precoated silica gel plastic plates and visualized by UV- irradiation, exposure to iodine vapors of spraying with KMnO₄ solution. IR spectra of liquid samples were run neat, and solids as KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer AC-1 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker WM-200 spectrometer (200 MHz) with tetramethylsilane as internal reference and mass spectra at 70 eV on a Jeol JMS-300 spectrometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000 spectrometer using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. C, H and N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba EA-1108 instrument at R.S.I.C., Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, India.

6-Aryl-2-chloro-3-cyano-4-methylthiopyridines (**2a-g**).

General procedure : 5-Aryl-3-cyano-4-methylthio-2*H*-pyridone (**1**; 1 mmol) in POCl₃ (10 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. Then the mixture was poured onto crushed ice and the desired product was isolated through column chromatography using 50% hexane in chloroform.

2-Chloro-3-cyano-6-phenyl-4-methylthiopyridine (2a) : It was synthesized from 3-cyano-6-phenyl-4-methylthio-2*H*-pyridone (0.20 g, 1 mmol) in POCl₃ as described above (yield 0.16 g, 61.54%), m.p. 130° (Found : C, 60.12; H, 3.62; N, 10.82. C₁₃H₉ClN₂S calcd for : C, 59.87; H, 3.48; N, 10.45%); *m/z* (%) 260 (M⁺, 100), 215 (3.4), 189 (18.3); *v*_{max} (KBr) 2218 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ(CDCl₃) 2.68 (3H, s, SCH₃), 7.43 (1H, s, ArH), 7.51 (3H, m, ArH), 8.00 (2H, m, ArH).

2-Chloro-3-cyano-6-(4-fluorophenyl)-4-methylthiopyridine (2b) : A reaction of 3-cyano-6-(4-fluorophenyl)-4-methylthio-2*H*-pyridone (0.26 g, 1 mmol) in POCl₃ afforded the title compound (yield 0.17 g, 61.15%), m.p. 190° (Found : C, 56.14; H, 2.87; N, 9.87. C₁₃H₈ClFN₂S calcd. for C, 56.00; H, 2.89; N, 10.04%); *m/z* (%) 278 (M⁺, 100), 233 (10), 207 (9.5); *v*_{max} (KBr) 2223 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ(CDCl₃) 2.68 (3H, s, SCH₃), 7.20 (2H, m, ArH), 7.38 (1H, s, ArH), 8.02 (2H, m, ArH).

2-Chloro-6-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-cyano-4-methylthiopyridine (2c) : It was prepared from 6-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-cyano-4-methylthio-2*H*-pyridone (0.28 g, 1 mmol) as described in preceding experiment (yield 0.15 g, 50.84%), m.p. 180° (Found : C, 52.65; H, 2.66; N, 9.29. C₁₃H₈Cl₂N₂S calcd. for : C, 52.89; H, 2.73; N, 9.49%); *m/z* (%) 295 (M⁺, 100), 260 (7.4), 138 (7); *v*_{max} (KBr) 2221 cm⁻¹ (CN);

δ (CDCl₃) 2.68 (3H, s, SCH₃), 7.39 (1H, s, ArH), 7.48 (2H, d, ArH), 7.96 (2H, d, ArH).

6-(4-Bromophenyl)-2-chloro-3-cyano-4-methylthiopyridine (2d): It was obtained by heating a mixture of 6-(4-bromophenyl)-3-cyano-4-methylthio-2H-pyridone (0.32 g, 1 mmol) and POCl₃ as described above (yield 0.18 g, 50.70%), m.p. 160° (Found: C, 45.72; H, 2.41; N, 7.96). C₁₃H₈BrClN₂S calcd. for: C, 45.97; H, 2.37; N, 8.25%; m/z (%) 340 (M⁺+1, 91); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2210 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ (CDCl₃) 2.66 (3H, s, SCH₃), 7.39 (1H, s, ArH), 7.64 (2H, d, ArH), 7.89 (2H, d, ArH).

2-Chloro-3-cyano-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylthiopyridine (2e): It was prepared from 2-cyano-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-methylthio-2H-pyridone (0.27 g, 1 mmol) and POCl₃ as described above (yield 0.16 g, 54.48%), m.p. 170° (Found: C, 38.10; H, 3.87; N, 9.72). C₁₄H₁₁ClN₂O₂S calcd. for: C, 57.82; H, 3.81; N, 9.63%; m/z (%) 291 (M⁺+1, 100); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2225 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ (CDCl₃) 2.66 (3H, s, SCH₃), 3.87 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.00 (2H, d, ArH), 7.35 (1H, s, ArH), 7.98 (2H, d, ArH).

2-Chloro-3-cyano-6-(2-furyl)-4-methylthiopyridine (2f): 3-Cyano-6-(2-furyl)-4-methylthio-2H-pyridone (0.23 g, 1 mmol) was refluxed in POCl₃ and yielded the title compound (yield 0.14 g, 51.85%), m.p. 175° (Found: C, 52.81; H, 2.90; N, 11.19). C₁₁H₇ClN₂O₂S calcd. for: C, 52.69; H, 2.82; N, 11.17%; m/z (%) 250 (M⁺, 100), 234 (15.8), 188 (14.6); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2227 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ (CDCl₃) 2.66 (3H, s, SCH₃), 6.61 (1H, m, ArH), 7.28 (1H, d, ArH), 7.38 (1H, s, ArH), 7.60 (1H, d, ArH).

2-Chloro-3-cyano-6-(2-thienyl)-4-methylthiopyridine (2g): It was synthesized from 3-cyano-6-(2-thienyl)-4-methylthio-2H-pyridone (0.26 g, 1 mmol) in POCl₃ as described above (yield 0.16 g, 60.15%), m.p. 160° (Found: C, 49.74; H, 2.82; N, 10.72). C₁₁H₇ClN₂S₂ calcd. for: C, 49.52; H, 2.65; N, 10.50%; m/z (%) 266 (M⁺, 24.5), 224 (100), 195 (8.2); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2230 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ (CDCl₃) 2.66 (3H, s, SCH₃), 7.15 (1H, m, ArH), 7.35 (1H, s, ArH), 7.56 (1H, d, ArH), 7.75 (1H, d, ArH).

Ethyl 3-amino-6-aryl-4-(carboethoxymethylsulfanyl)thieno[2,3-b]pyridino-2-carboxylates (3a-c). *General procedure*: A mixture of 6-aryl-2-chloro-3-cyano-4-methylthiopyridine (2; 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.03 g sodium in 10 ml ethanol) was refluxed for 10–12 h. Then excess of ethanol was removed under reduced pressure and neutralized with 10% HCl. A yellow solid thus obtained was filtered and purified from silica gel column using 1% methanol in chloroform as eluent.

Ethyl 3-amino-6-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-(carboethoxy-

methylsulfanyl)thieno[2,3-b]pyridine-2-carboxylate (3a): It was obtained from the reaction of 2c (0.29 g, 1 mmol) with ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in NaOEt (0.03 g Na in 10 ml ethanol) as described above (yield 0.16 g, 35.56%), m.p. 180° (Found: C, 53.32; H, 4.24; N, 6.27). C₂₀H₁₉ClN₂O₄S₂ calcd. for: C, 53.26; H, 4.25; N, 6.21%; m/z (%) 451 (M⁺+1, 96.3), 405 (39.3), 376 (100); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1650 (C=O), 3354 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.23 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.39 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.17 (2H, q, CH₂), 4.20 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.36 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.70 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.44 (2H, d, ArH), 7.70 (1H, s, ArH), 7.98 (2H, d, ArH).

Ethyl 3-amino-6-(4-bromophenyl)-4-(carboethoxymethylsulfanyl)thieno[2,3-b]pyridine-2-carboxylate (3b): It was synthesized from the reaction of 2d (0.36 g, 1 mmol) with ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.03 g Na in 10 ml ethanol) as described above (yield 0.21 g, 42.12%), m.p. 172° (Found: C, 48.56; H, 3.95; N, 5.78). C₂₀H₁₉BrN₂O₄S₂ calcd. for: C, 48.48; H, 3.86; N, 5.65%; m/z (%) 495 (M⁺, 100), 450 (52.2), 422 (10); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1652 (C=O), 3360 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.25 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.43 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.06 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.18 (2H, q, CH₂), 4.35 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.70 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.61 (2H, d, ArH), 7.72 (1H, s, ArH), 7.72 (2H, d, ArH).

Ethyl 3-amino-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-(carboethoxymethylsulfanyl)thieno[2,3-b]pyridine-2-carboxylate (3c): It was prepared by the reaction of 2e (0.29 g, 1 mmol) with ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in 10 ml ethanol) as described above (yield 0.20 g, 44.84%), m.p. 160° (Found: C, 56.58; H, 5.10; N, 6.35). C₂₁H₂₂N₂O₅S₂ calcd. for: C, 56.49; H, 4.96; N, 6.27%; m/z (%) 446 (100), 400 (30.7), 371 (80.7); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1660 (C=O), 3362 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.25 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.45 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.92 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.22 (2H, q, CH₂), 4.39 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.70 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.04 (2H, d, ArH), 7.27 (1H, s, ArH), 8.08 (2H, d, ArH).

Ethyl 3-amino-6-aryl-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[3,2-c]pyridine-2-carboxylates (4a-e). *General procedure*: A mixture of 6-aryl-3-cyano-4-methylthio-2H-pyridone (1; 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.03 g Na in 10 ml ethanol) was refluxed for 15–18 h. After completion of reaction, mixture was poured into ice water and neutralized with 10% HCl. The solid thus obtained was filtered and the desired product was isolated from column chromatography using 2% methanol in chloroform as eluent.

Ethyl 3-amino-6-(4-bromophenyl)-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[3,2-c]pyridine-2-carboxylate (4a): A mixture

of 6-(4-bromophenyl)-3-cyano-4-methylthio-2*H*-pyridone (**1a**; 0.32 g, 1 mmol) and ethylmercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in 10 ml ethanol) was refluxed for 15–18 h to afford the product (yield 0.22 g, 55.98%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 48.93; H, 3.69; N, 7.25. C₁₆H₁₃BrN₂O₃S calcd. for : C, 48.86; H, 3.33; N, 7.12%; *m/z* (%) 393 (M⁺, 100), 367 (247), 347 (20.6), 321 (55.9); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1660 (C=O), 1685 (C=O), 3411 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.30 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.27 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.95 (1H, s, ArH), 7.23 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.73 (4H, s, ArH), 11.94 (1H, s, NH).

*Ethyl 3-amino-6-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[2,3-*c*]pyridine-2-carboxylate (4b)* : It was obtained by refluxing a mixture of **1b** (0.27 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in 10 ml EtOH) as described above (yield 0.18 g, 52.93%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 59.41; H, 4.72; N, 8.17. C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₄S calcd. for : C, 59.30; H, 4.68; N, 8.13%; *m/z* (%) 344 (M⁺, 73.2), 316 (15.9), 297 (10.1), 200 (48.3); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1675 (C=O), 1690 (C=O), 3423 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.33 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.87 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.28 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.07 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.09 (2H, d, ArH), 7.12 (1H, s, ArH), 7.78 (2H, d, ArH), 11.92 (1H, s, NH).

*Ethyl 3-amino-6-(2-thienyl)-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[3,2-*c*]pyridine-2-carboxylate (4c)* : It was synthesized from **1c** (0.26 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in 12 ml EtOH) as described in the preceding experiment (yield 0.17 g, 52.4%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 52.55; H, 3.94; N, 8.78. C₁₄H₁₂N₂O₃S₂ calcd. for : C, 52.48; H, 3.78; N, 8.74%; *m/z* (%) 320 (M⁺, 75), 296 (18.7), 277 (14.2), 204 (100); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1670 (C=O), 1690 (C=O), 3471 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.39 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.30 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.75 (1H, s, ArH), 7.01 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.13 (1H, m, ArH), 7.44 (1H, d, ArH), 7.78 (1H, d, ArH), 11.32 (1H, br s, NH).

*Ethyl 3-amino-6-(2-furyl)-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[3,2-*c*]pyridine-2-carboxylate (4d)* : It was synthesized from **1d** (0.33 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in NaOEt (0.03 g Na in ethanol) as described above (yield 0.17 g, 55.92%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 55.32; H, 4.03; N, 9.27. C₁₄H₁₂N₂O₄S calcd. for : C, 55.25; H, 3.97; N, 9.23%; *m/z* (%) 304 (M⁺, 100), 276 (34.7), 258 (38.1), 232 (69.9); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1660 (C=O), 3150 (NH), 3412 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.47 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.39 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.85 (1H, s, ArH), 7.26 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.60 (1H, m, ArH), 8.05 (1H, d, ArH), 8.43 (1H, d, ArH), 12.00 (1H, br s, NH).

*Ethyl 3-amino-6-(4-bromophenyl)-7-cyano-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[3,2-*c*]pyridine-2-carboxylate (4e)* : It was obtained from **1e** (0.35 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in ethanol) as described above (yield 0.22 g, 52.63%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 48.97; H, 2.95; N, 10.15. C₁₇H₁₂BrN₃O₃S calcd. for : C, 48.81; H, 2.89; N, 10.07%; *m/z* (%) 418 (M⁺, 100); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1660 (C=O), 1695 (C=O), 2210 (CN), 3452 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.32 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.28 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.85 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.73 (2H, d, ArH), 7.82 (2H, d, ArH), 11.90 (1H, s, NH).

*Ethyl 3-amino-6-(4-bromophenyl)-5-methyl-4-oxo-4,5-dihydrothieno[3,2-*c*]pyridine-2-carboxylate (5)* : A mixture of **4a** (0.39 g, 1 mmol), K₂CO₃ (0.13 g, 1 mmol) in DMF (10 ml) was stirred for 30 min, then methyl iodide (0.10 ml, 1 mmol) was added dropwise at room temperature and stirred for 4 h. Then the mixture was poured into water and the solid thus obtained was crystallized from methanol (yield 0.20 g, 49.14%), m.p. 185° (Found : C, 50.16; H, 3.78; N, 6.95. C₁₇H₁₅BrN₂O₃S calcd. for : C, 50.12; H, 3.71; N, 6.88%; *m/z* (%) 407 (M⁺, 100), 379 (34.1), 360 (50), 334 (57.7); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1666 (C=O), 1690 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.36 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.36 (3H, s, NCH₃), 4.32 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.44 (1H, s, ArH), 7.24 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.27 (2H, d, ArH), 7.62 (2H, d, ArH).

*6-Aryl-4-methylsulfanyl-1*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridin-3-amines (6a-g)*. *General procedure* : A mixture of 6-aryl-2-chloro-3-cyano-4-methylthiopyridine (**2**; 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol was refluxed for 6–7 h, and the resulting solid was crystallized from methanol.

*4-Methylsulfanyl-6-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridin-3-amine (6a)* : It was prepared from **2a** (0.26 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) as described above (yield 0.16 g, 62.5%), m.p. 220° (Found : C, 61.21; H, 4.77; N, 21.93. C₁₃H₁₂N₄S calcd. for : C, 60.91; H, 4.72; N, 21.86%; *m/z* (%) 256 (M⁺, 100), 240 (2.2), 209 (7.9); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3133 (NH), 3354 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.69 (3H, s, SCH₃), 4.41 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.14 (1H, s, ArH), (3H, d, ArH), 7.98–8.20 (2H, m, ArH).

*6-(4-Fluorophenyl)-4-methylsulfanyl-1*H*-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridin-3-amine (6b)* : It was obtained from **2b** (0.28 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) as described above (yield 0.17 g, 62.04%), m.p. 210° (Found : C, 56.82; H, 4.02; N, 20.33. C₁₃H₁₁FN₄S calcd. for : C, 56.92; H, 4.0; N, 20.42%; *m/z* (%) 274 (M⁺, 100), 258 (19.3), 227 (12.5); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3150 (NH), 3450 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.69 (3H, s, SCH₃), 4.40 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.08 (1H, s, ArH), 7.17–7.19 (2H, m, ArH), 7.97–7.99 (2H, m, ArH).

6-(4-Chlorophenyl)-4-methylsulfanyl-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridin-3-amine (6c): It was synthesized by refluxing **2c** (0.29 g, 1 mmol) with hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) as described in the preceding experiment (yield 0.16 g, 55.17%), m.p. 225° (Found : C, 53.74; H, 3.96; N, 19.39. $C_{13}H_{11}ClN_4S$ calcd. for : C, 53.69; H, 3.81; N, 19.27%); m/z (%) 290 (M^+ , 100), 290 (100), 218 (31.8), 186 (23.8); ν_{max} (KBr) 3143 (NH), 3417 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.69 (3H, s, SCH_3), 4.40 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.08 (1H, s, ArH), 7.47 (2H, d, ArH), 7.94 (2H, d, ArH).

6-(4-Bromophenyl)-4-methylsulfanyl-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridin-3-amine (6d): It was synthesized similarly from **2d** (0.34 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol as described earlier (yield 0.20 g, 56.35%), m.p. 210° (Found : C, 46.56; H, 3.52; N, 16.92. $C_{13}H_{11}BrN_4S$ calcd. for : C, 46.56; H, 3.31; N, 16.71%); m/z 335 (M^+ , 100), 288 (7), 179 (9.4); ν_{max} (KBr) 3160 (NH), 3446 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.69 (3H, s, SCH_3), 4.44 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.09 (1H, s, ArH), 7.62 (2H, d, ArH), 7.88 (2H, d, ArH).

6-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-methylsulfanyl-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridin-3-amine (6e): It was synthesized similarly from **2e** (0.29 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol as described earlier (yield 0.17 g, 60%), m.p. 128° (Found : C, 58.96; H, 4.97; N, 19.72. $C_{14}H_{14}N_4OS$ calcd. for : C, 58.72; H, 4.93; N, 19.57%); m/z 286 (M^+ , 100); ν_{max} (KBr) 3135 (NH), 3476 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.68 (3H, s, SCH_3), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.40 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.00–7.03 (2H, m, ArH), 7.09 (1H, s, ArH), 7.94–7.98 (2H, m, ArH).

6-(2-Furyl)-4-methylsulfanyl-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridin-3-amine (6f): It was prepared from **2f** (0.27 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) as described above (yield 0.14 g, 56.91%), m.p. 225° (Found : C, 53.78; H, 4.16; N, 22.92. $C_{11}H_{10}N_4OS$ calcd. for : C, 53.64; H, 4.09; N, 22.75%); m/z 246 (M^+ , 100), 231 (11.6), 159 (4.5); ν_{max} (KBr) 3140 (NH), 3334 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.69 (3H, s, SCH_3), 4.36 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.58 (1H, m, ArH), 7.14 (1H, d, ArH), 7.26 (1H, d, ArH), 7.58 (1H, s, ArH).

4-Methylsulfanyl-6-(2-thienyl)-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridin-3-amine (6g): It was prepared from **2g** (0.27 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) as described above (yield 0.16 g, 61.07%), m.p. 205° (Found : C, 50.54; H, 3.84; N, 21.61. $C_{11}H_{10}N_4S_2$ calcd. for : C, 50.36; H, 3.84; N, 21.36%); m/z 262 (M^+ , 82.3), 247 (8.1), 216 (11.8); ν_{max} (KBr) 3130 (NH), 3402 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.68 (3H, s, SCH_3), 4.40 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.09 (1H, s, ArH), 7.14 (1H, m, ArH), 7.45 (1H, d, ArH), 7.67 (1H, d, ArH).

Ethyl 3-amino-4,6-disubstitutedthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-6-carboxylates (9a-f). **General procedure** : A mixture of 5-cyano-2,4-disubstituted-6-methylsulfanyl-pyrimidine (**7**; 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (**8**; 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.03 g sodium in 10 ml ethanol) was refluxed for 8–10 h. After completion of reaction, excess of ethanol was removed under reduced pressure upto minimum concentration and then neutralized with 10% HCl. A solid thus obtained was crystallized from methanol.

Ethyl 3-amino-4-hydroxythieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate (9a) : A mixture of **7a** (0.17 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.03 g Na in 10 ml ethanol) was refluxed to afford the title compound (yield 0.11 g, 46.03%), m.p. >240° (Found : C, 45.21; H, 3.85; N, 17.62. $C_9H_9N_2O_3S$ calcd. for : C, 45.18; H, 3.79; N, 17.56%); m/z (%) 239 (M^+ , 60.8), 211 (20), 193 (56), 167 (61); ν_{max} (KBr) 1652 (C=O), 1701 (C=O), 3448 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ; δ ($DMSO-d_6$) 1.28 (3H, t, CH_3), 4.30 (2H, q, CH_2), 6.87 (2H, br s, NH_2), 8.18 (1H, s, ArH).

Ethyl 3-amino-4-hydroxy-6-methylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate (9b) : It was synthesized from **7b** (0.18 g, 1 mmol), ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in 20 ml ethanol) as described above (yield 0.13 g, 51.38%), m.p. 245° (Found : C, 47.49; H, 4.42; N, 16.67. $C_{10}H_{11}N_3O_3S$ calcd. for : C, 47.42; H, 4.38; N, 16.59%); m/z (%) 253 (M^+ , 20), 225 (10), 208 (12); ν_{max} (KBr) 1650 (C=O), 1689 (C=O), 3454 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ; δ ($DMSO-d_6$) 1.28 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.38 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.22 (2H, q, CH_2), 6.8 (2H, br s, NH_2).

Ethyl 3-amino-4-hydroxy-6-trifluoromethylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate (9c) : It was obtained from the reaction of **7c** (0.24 g, 1 mmol) with ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in 10 ml ethanol) as described above (yield 0.15 g, 48.86%), m.p. 260° (Found : C, 39.17; H, 2.69; N, 13.72. $C_{10}H_8F_3N_3O_3S$ calcd. for : C, 39.09; H, 2.62; N, 13.68%); m/z (%) 307 (M^+ , 20), 270 (11.7), 238 (70.9), 192 (97.6); ν_{max} (KBr) 1647 (C=O), 1697 (C=O), 3475 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ; δ ($DMSO-d_6$) 1.15 (3H, t, CH_3), 14.13 (2H, q, CH_2), 6.56 (2H, br s, NH_2).

Ethyl 3,4-diamino-6-phenylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate (9d) : It was synthesized from **7d** (0.24 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in ethanol) as described above (yield 0.16 g, 50.96%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 57.41; H, 4.52; N, 17.87. $C_{15}H_{14}N_4O_2S$ calcd. for : C, 57.31; H, 4.49; N, 17.82%); m/z (%) 314 (M^+ , 87.1), 286 (16.5), 269 (22.9), 242 (69.4); ν_{max} (KBr) 1660 (C=O), 3365 (NH_2) cm^{-1} ;

δ (CDCl₃) 1.29 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.26 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.89 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.58 (3H, m, ArH), 7.64 (2H, br s, NH₂), 8.21 (2H, m, ArH).

Ethyl 3,4-diamino-6-(2-pyridyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate (9e) : It was obtained from **7e** (0.20 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in NaOEt (0.03 g Na in EtOH) as described earlier (yield 0.16 g, 50.79%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 53.37; H, 4.21; N, 22.30. C₁₄H₁₃N₄O₂S calcd. for : C, 53.32; H, 4.15; N, 22.20%; *m/z* (%) 315 (M⁺, 100), 269 (19.7), 243 (63.9); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1685 (C=O), 3460 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.38 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.40 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.29 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.58 (1H, m, PyH), 7.85 (2H, br s, NH₂), 8.08 (1H, m, PyH), 8.44 (1H, d, PyH), 8.81 (1H, d, PyH).

Ethyl 3,4-diamino-6-(4-pyridyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-6-carboxylate (9f) : It was synthesized from **7f** (0.24 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in 10 ml EtOH) as described above (yield 0.16 g, 50.79%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 53.40; H, 4.23; N, 22.31. C₁₄H₁₃N₅O₂S calcd. for : C, 53.32; H, 4.15; N, 22.20%; *m/z* (%) 315 (M⁺, 49), 269 (25); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1682 (C=O), 3462 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.38 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.30 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.16 (2H, br s, NH₂), 8.85 (2H, br s, NH₂), 8.26 (2H, d, PyH), 8.80 (2H, d, PyH).

Ethyl 3-amino-4-oxo-9aH-pyrido[1,2-a]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2-carboxylate (11a) : A mixture of 2-methylsulfanyl-4-oxo-4H-pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidine-3-carboxylate (**10a**; 0.22 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in NaOEt (prepared from 0.03 g Na in 10 ml ethanol) was refluxed for 7–8 h. After completion, the reaction mixture was acidified with 10% HCl and the solid thus obtained was crystallized from methanol (yield 0.22 g, 76.12%), m.p. 195° (Found : C, 54.07; H, 3.96; N, 14.61. C₁₃H₁₁N₃O₃S calcd. for : C, 53.97; H, 3.83; N, 14.52%; *m/z* (%) 290 (M⁺+1, 100), 261 (27.9), 243 (45.4), 217 (37.3); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1651 (C=O), 1703 (C=O), 3452 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.31 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.27 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.83 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.00 (1H, t, ArH), 7.49 (1H, d, ArH), 7.69 (1H, m, ArH), 8.89 (1H, d, ArH).

Ethyl 3-amino-7-chloro-4-oxo-9aH-pyrido[1,2-a]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2-carboxylate (11b) : It was synthesized from **10b** (0.25 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in ethanol) as described above (yield 0.17 g, 52.63%), m.p. 212° (Found : C, 48.36; H, 3.18; N, 13.08. C₁₀H₁₀ClN₃O₃S calcd. for : C, 48.22; H, 3.11; N, 12.98%; *m/z* (%) 323 (M⁺, 100), 295 (13), 278 (11.5), 251 (44.9); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1641 (C=O), 1695 (C=O), 3460 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.39 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.34 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.87 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.60 (2H, m, ArH), 8.97 (1H, s, ArH).

Ethyl 3-amino-7-methyl-4-oxo-9aH-pyrido[1,2-a]thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-2-carboxylate (11c) : It was prepared from 7-methyl-2-methylsulfanyl-4-oxo-4H-pyrido[1,2-d]pyrimidine-3-carbonitrile (**10c**; 0.23 g, 1 mmol) and ethyl mercaptoacetate (0.12 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in ethanol) as described above (yield 0.22 g, 72.61%), m.p. 205° (Found : C, 55.50; H, 4.38; N, 13.94. C₁₄H₁₃N₃O₃S calcd. for : C, 55.43; H, 4.32; N, 13.85%; *m/z* (%) 303 (M⁺, 100), 275 (27.1), 230 (13.8); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1652 (C=O), 1693 (C=O), 3460 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.38 (3H, t, CH₃), 2.40 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.34 (2H, q, CH₂), 6.87 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.46 (2H, m, ArH), 7.69 (1H, s, ArH).

9-Methyl-12H-pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimido[4',5'] : 4,5]-thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-4,12(3H)dione (12) : It was obtained by refluxing **11c** (0.30 g, 1 mmol) in formamide for 12–15 h. The mixture was then poured in ice-water. The solid thus obtained was filtered and the product was isolated on silica gel column chromatography using 4% methanol in chloroform as eluent (yield 0.14 g, 49.30%), m.p. 260° (Found : C, 55.10; H, 2.95; N, 19.87. C₁₃H₈N₄O₂S calcd. for : C, 54.92; H, 2.84; N, 19.71%; *m/z* (%) 284 (M⁺, 4), 270 (60.5), 242 (14.6); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1660 (C=O) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.53 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.69 (1H, d, ArH), 7.81 (1H, d, ArH), 8.14 (1H, s, ArH), 9.40 (1H, s, ArH).

4-Amino-5-oxo-5H-pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimido[4,5-d]pyrimidin-2-ylcyanamide (13a) : It was prepared from **10a** (0.22 g, 1 mmol), dicyandiamide (0.08 g, 1 mmol) in sodium ethoxide (0.23 g Na in 10 ml ethanol). The mixture was neutralized with 10% HCl and the solid obtained was filtered. Finally, the desired product was isolated through column chromatography using 5% methanol in chloroform as eluent (yield 0.13 g, 51.38%), m.p. >260° (Found : C, 52.25; H, 2.85; N, 38.88. C₁₁H₇N₇O calcd. for : C, 52.17; H, 2.79; N, 38.72%; *m/z* (%) 253 (M⁺, 7.2), 214 (5.4), 196 (9.6); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1641 (C=O), 2204 (CN), 3155 (NH), 3450 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 6.63 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.52 (1H, t, ArH), 7.72 (1H, d, ArH), 8.01 (1H, m, ArH), 8.86 (1H, d, ArH).

4-Amino-8-methyl-5-oxo-5H-pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidin-2-ylcyanamide (13b) : It was synthesized from **10c** (0.23 g, 1 mmol), dicyandiamide (0.08 g, 1 mmol) and sodium ethoxide (0.03 g Na in ethanol) as described above (yield 0.14 g, 52.43%), m.p. 260° (Found : C, 54.10; H, 3.45; N, 36.73. C₁₂H₉N₇O calcd. for : C, 53.93; H, 3.39; N, 36.69%; *m/z* (%) 267 (M⁺, 60), 228 (20), 216 (59.9); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1662 (C=O), 2220 (CN), 3166 (NH), 3430 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.12 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.61 (2H, m, ArH), 8.22 (1H, s, ArH).

3-Aminopyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidin-4-(1H)-one (14a) A mixture of **10a** (0.22 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. After cooling, the solid thus obtained was crystallized from methanol (yield 0.14 g, 69.65%), m.p. >260° (Found: C, 53.85, H, 3.67, N, 34.94. C₉H₇N₅O calcd: for C, 53.73, H, 3.51, N, 34.81%), m/z (%) 201 (M⁺, 100), 143 (18:1); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1665 (C=O), 3460 (NH₂) cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-d₆) 6.80 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.03 (1H, m, ArH), 7.40 (1H, d, ArH), 7.71 (1H, m, ArH), 8.82 (1H, d, ArH), 12.03 (1H, br s, NH).

3-Amino-7-methylpyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidin-4-(1H)-one (14b) It was prepared from **10c** (0.23 g, 1 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) as described above (yield 0.14 g, 65.12%), m.p. 260° (Found: C, 55.94, H, 4.29, N, 32.70. C₁₀H₉N₅O calcd: for C, 55.81, H, 4.21, N, 32.5%), m/z (%) 215 (4.5), 160 (12.9), $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1667 (C=O), 3455 (NH₂) cm⁻¹, δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.34 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.49 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.30 (1H, d, ArH), 7.60 (1H, d, ArH), 8.55 (1H, s, ArH), 12.15 (1H, br s, NH).

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